

ENSURING CYBERSECURITY AS THE MAIN PROBLEM OF DIGITAL
TRANSFORMATION OF BUSINESS PROCESSES

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Abstract. *This article examines the processes of digital transformation of the economy at the current stage of development.*

Keywords: *digital economy, digitalization, digital business processes, cybersecurity.*

ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ КИБЕРБЕЗОПАСНОСТИ КАК ОСНОВНАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА
ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ БИЗНЕС-ПРОЦЕССОВ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются процессы цифровой трансформации экономики на современном этапе развития.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровая экономика, цифровизация, цифровые бизнес-процессы, кибербезопасность.*

The growth of digital technologies being introduced into various business processes has revealed a number of problem areas in cybersecurity issues. The article examines the trends in the development of the shadow digital market and identifies the most popular offers on it. An analysis of the areas of investment in digital technologies has shown that enterprises in 2022 spend the most money on technologies that ensure cybersecurity. It has been established that organizations require not only modern technologies and financial resources, but also highly qualified, reliable personnel to ensure and maintain information security. Keywords: Digitalization, cybersecurity, digital technologies, digital transformation, business processes, shadow market The 21st century can be confidently called the century of digital transformation of all business processes occurring both at the macro and micro levels. In order to survive and ensure their competitiveness in modern realities, organizations need to create and use new development strategies, the main place in which is given to digital technologies. The growth of digital technologies introduced into various business processes, which occurred under the influence of the pandemic period, revealed a number of problem areas in cybersecurity issues. Every year, organizations in all fields of activity use and store more and more customer data, and therefore issues related to ensuring the security of personal data have become a priority for both commercial enterprises and government agencies. The digital transformation of the economy involves the provision and use of personal data, for example, when registering on mail servers, remote registration of financial products or subscriptions, which in

turn leads to the expansion of databases and an increase in the volume of the market for illegal trade in personal data. According to Group-IB, the number of unsecured databases in Russia has already increased by 37% in 2022 alone.

2022 An analysis of the investment activity of enterprises showed that cloud technologies were the most in demand in 2021, investments in which were considered a priority by more than half of the world's leading companies. However, in 2022, enterprises began to choose cybersecurity technologies as the main investment area.

The volume of the shadow market for access to information resources of companies is constantly increasing, which is primarily due to the involvement of an increasing number of organizations in the processes of digital transformation.

Special forums and marketplaces on the darknet (DarkNet) serve as a digital platform for trading personal data, where transactions are most often carried out through an intermediary. There are two main segments in the domestic market of illegal trade in personal data: – sale of databases; – search and sale of a package of personal data for a specific person. As for the source, personal data is obtained either by hacking or by bribing an employee who works in a certain organization and has access to databases of interest. Often, the reason for hacking is the insufficiently attentive attitude of administrators and developers to cybersecurity issues, since database servers, as a rule, have a default security configuration, which makes the system vulnerable. Thus, organizations need not only modern technologies and financial resources to ensure and maintain information security, but also highly qualified, and most importantly reliable personnel. The shadow digital market is constantly changing, influenced by the current economic situation, the growing skill level and technical capabilities of cybercriminals and the demands from potential buyers. The analysis showed that in 2022, the most popular offers on the shadow market include the following.

- Access to Active Directory accounts. This information is one of the most valuable and in demand in the shadow market, as it allows an attacker to freely distribute malicious software across all networks of an organization (enterprise).
- Initial Network Access (RDP, VPN, SSH)). The most frequently sold information on the shadow market. Working remotely, employees need access to corporate resources, and this is what cybercriminals use by scanning and hacking RDP servers.
- Access to information using a web shell. This script is used to manage other people's servers and websites. Most often, it provides access to the file system, databases, and allows you to crack a password by going through possible combinations.
- Access to remote monitoring and management of IT systems.
- A CMS administrator account that provides access to web hosting content. The analysis showed that access to personal digital information is based on several weak

points (gaps), they can be prevented using standard cybersecurity measures, which are often neglected by users. These measures include: using a strong password, enabling two-factor authentication, frequent account verification, etc. In addition, constant monitoring of the shadow market (darknet forums and trading platforms) will help identify potentially dangerous offers and take appropriate measures to ensure cybersecurity. Thus, the main problem of the digital transformation of the domestic economy at the present stage is to ensure its security and cyber stability. Theft of digital information, hacking of user profiles, identification errors, all this reduces trust in digital technologies and slows down the overall processes of digital transformation of the economy.

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